

FATIGUE DAMAGE MECHANISMS IN BORON-ALUMINIUM COMPOSITE LAMINATES

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One unidirectional and two laminated 6061-0 Al-B composite plates were tested under various loading conditions in uniaxial tension. Three distinct types of material response to cyclic loading were identified: No evidence of damage at low loads; damage accumulation at moderate to high loads, caused primarily by growth of long fatigue cracks in the matrix parallel to the fibers within off-axis layers; and sudden, localized failure of the fibers at loads exceeding the endurance limit.

Quantitative analysis of the results shows that the onset of internal damage, demonstrated by a gradual reduction in axial elastic modulus with the increasing number of load cycles, depends on the applied stress range and is independent of the mean stress. The stress range at which damage first starts to appear coincides with the shakedown range, both in unidirectional and laminated plates. Since the aluminum matrix is strained elastically after the composite shakes down, it is concluded that the long fatigue cracks in the off-axis layers are caused by cyclic plastic straining of the matrix when the composite is loaded beyond the shakedown range. The magnitude of this range, which is relatively small in certain laminates, can be predicted from theoretical considerations and from measured cyclic strain response of the matrix material.

If the applied stress range causes fatigue damage but is smaller than that required for fatigue failure, there is evidence that after about 1×10^6 cycles a certain saturation damage state is reached which depends on the applied stresses and remains essentially unchanged with increasing number of cycles. The existence of this damage state can be related to the growth of long matrix cracks in the off-axis layers. As these layers lose elastic stiffness due to fatigue cracking, the internal stresses in the laminate are transferred to the zero-degree layers. The unloading of the off-axis layers eventually leads to arrest of matrix crack growth.

Observed stiffness reductions in the saturation damage state ranged from about 8% in unidirectional specimens, to 50% in quasi-isotropic laminates. Fiber breaks prior to failure have been found only in specimens tested at loads approaching their endurance limits.

INTRODUCTION

The possible relationship between fatigue and shakedown in metal matrix composites was first suggested by Dvorak and Tarn [1] and related to then available experimental data, obtained primarily for unidirectional 6061 Al-B materials. In the present paper, the relationship is examined theoretically and experimentally for both unidirectional and laminated 6061-0 Al-B composites.

The plan of the paper is as follows: First, we summarize recent results on evaluation of shakedown limits in laminated plates. Next, we present results of tensile fatigue test on 6061-0 aluminum, 6061-0 Al-B unidirectional materials, and two (0/±45/90) laminated plates. We show the existence of a definite relationship between shakedown and the onset of fatigue damage in the laminates. In particular, no fatigue damage takes place if the applied stress range is such that the material remains elastic, or shakes down, i.e., resumes elastic cyclic straining after a small number of plastic strain cycles. Fatigue damage occurs only in specimens which are subjected to stress ranges which cause sustained cyclic plastic straining in the aluminum matrix. If the applied stress range is smaller than that required for fatigue failure, there is evidence that after about 1×10^6 cycles a certain damage state is reached which remains essentially unchanged with increasing number of cycles. This is referred to as a "saturation damage state."

Furthermore, we show that a major source of fatigue damage in the laminated specimens are long cracks which grow in the aluminum matrix parallel to the fibers in the off-axis layers. The presence of these cracks leads to a reduction of the elastic stiffness of the off-axis layers, and thus to transfer of the internal stresses to the zero-degree layers. The unloading of the off-axis layers eventually arrests the matrix crack growth, hence the saturation damage state is reached. It follows that the saturation damage state in a given composite material depends on the laminate lay-up, and on the loading history. Many different damage levels are reached at different applied stress levels. Unlike the shakedown state, which is related only to the stress range and is independent of the mean stress, the saturation damage level may depend on stress amplitude and mean stress.

SHAKEDOWN ANALYSIS

According to the first shakedown theorem or Melan's theorem [2,3] an elastic-plastic body will shake down, i.e., resume elastic straining after several plastic strain cycles, for an arbitrary program of variable repeated loads within prescribed limits, if any time-independent state of residual stress (selfstress) can be found such that superposition of this state and the elastic response for all possible combinations of external forces within the prescribed limits will not lead to stresses at or above yield at any point [4,5]. It is self-evident that the initial yield surface, or any subsequent load surface, represents a lower bound on the shakedown limits of the structure.

The application of Melan's theorem to shakedown of unidirectional composites was presented in [6], and the extension to laminated plates was discussed in [7]. These and other related results [8-10] show the construction of initial yield surfaces for composite laminates, the translation of these surfaces in the load space during plastic loading, and their identification with shakedown envelopes.

Fig. 1 and 2 illustrate the procedure. The overall yield surface of the laminate is an internal envelope of the yield surfaces of individual plies, which are shown in Fig. 1 for the case of a quasi-isotropic B-Al plate under biaxial in-plane stresses S_{11} and S_{22} ; Y is the tension yield strength of the aluminum matrix. Each of the plies has its own elliptical yield surface in the composite stress space, which was constructed in this particular case from the local stress distribution in the matrix and the Mises yield condition. Fig. 2 shows the internal envelope, i.e., the overall initial yield surface, and the translation and deformation of this overall yield surface in the process of plastic loading along the S_{11} axis, from the origin to $S_{11}/Y=3.0$. The deformation of the overall yield surface is the result of the relative translation of the three local yield surfaces in the biaxial loading plane.

Each of the local surfaces translates according to its own hardening rule [9-11]. After loading to $S_{11}/Y=3.0$, the composite will remain elastic for any loading path within the current yield surface. In the case of cyclic loading the three surfaces will translate so as to accommodate the loading range within the overall yield surface, i.e., in the elastic region. If such an accommodation is possible, the composite will shake down, and the current yield surface will be the shakedown envelope.

FIGURE 1

Yield surfaces of a B-Al laminated plate loaded by in-plane biaxial normal stresses. The S_{11} direction coincides with 0° fiber direction.

FIGURE 2

Initial and current yield surfaces of the laminated B-Al plate of Fig. 1 after loading to $S_{11}/Y=3.0$. The S_{11} direction coincides with 0° fiber direction.

In concluding this section, we list the magnitudes of the dimensionless shakedown limits $\Delta S_{sh}/Y$ for materials which have been used in the experimental program. In each case we consider load applied in the 0° fiber direction, and the following material properties:

$$E_f = 40 \times 10^4 \text{MPa}, E_m = 7.25 \times 10^4 \text{MPa}, \nu_f = 0.2098, \nu_m = 0.3291.$$

TABLE I. Shakedown Limits $\Delta S_{sh}/Y$
of Selected B-Al Composite Laminates

LAYUP	ν_f	$\Delta S_{sh}/Y$
$(0/\pm 45/90/0/\pm 45/\pm 90)_S$	0.45	2.7
$(0/\pm 45/90)_S$	0.33	2.6
Unidirectional	0.45	6.1

The magnitude of $\Delta S_{sh}/Y$ indicates the diameter of the yield surface section with the load axis, e.g., S_{11} in Fig. 1 and 2. The magnitude of Y should be determined from fatigue tests on the matrix material, as described in the sequel. Certain parameters used in calculating the values listed in Table I were different from those used in Fig. 1 and 2. Therefore, the values of $\Delta S_{sh}/Y$ are not exactly equal to yield surface diameters which can be measured in the Figures.

EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

1. Specimen Preparation and Testing

Material for boron-aluminum composite specimens was manufactured by DWA Composite Specialties, Inc., in the form of 12 in. by 9 in. plates. The matrix was 6061 aluminum, fibers were 5.6 mils diameter boron. Plates were cut with a diamond saw into rectangular coupons 10.16 cm (4.0 in.) long and 1.27 cm (0.5 in.) wide. All specimens were annealed at 413°C (775°F) for two hours and cooled at the rate of about 28°C (50°F) per hour from the annealing temperature to 260°C (500°F). Each specimen was inspected using C-scan after annealing. This examination revealed internal defects. Specimens with no defects were designated as good (G), specimens with moderate amounts of defects as defective (D), and those with many defects as very defective (VD). Four rectangular tabs made of unidirectional glass-epoxy composite were adhesively bonded to each composite specimen. Tab dimensions were 0.32 cm (0.125 in.) thick and 2.86 cm (1.125 in.) long. All fatigue failures occurred in the gage section, none in the vicinity of the tab area.

The 6061-0 aluminum specimens were cut from a sheet supplied by DWA. The specimens were cut as rectangular coupons 12.7 cm (5.0 in.) long, 1.27 cm (0.5 in.) wide, and 0.2 cm (0.079 in.) thick, and then machined to a "dog-bone" type specimen with the average gage section area 0.825 cm (0.325 in.) by 0.2 cm (0.079 in.). These specimens were then annealed and provided with 2024-T6 aluminum tabs, which were similar in size to those used with the composite specimens.

Fatigue testing was conducted on a MTS closed-loop system, in load controlled tension-tension mode. Standard wedge grips were used. Specimen strain was measured with a MTS extensometer, 2.54 cm (1.0 in.) gage length, designed for fatigue testing. An X-Y plotter was used to record the load-strain response. When converted to stress strain units, the typical response of a cyclically loaded specimen is shown schematically in Fig. 3. Both elastic and elastic-plastic strains were observed in specimens tested at cyclic load amplitudes exceeding material shakedown limits. The width of the loop decreased somewhat during cyclic loading, usually after 10^4 cycles in lami-

nated specimens; this may be due to a combination of cyclic hardening of the matrix and progressive matrix cracking which may contribute to load transfer to the fibers.

FIGURE 3
Schematic stress-strain diagram of cyclically loaded tension-tension specimens.

2. 6061-0 Aluminum Test Results

Unreinforced aluminum specimens were fatigue tested to determine the extent of cyclic hardening that may be expected to occur in the matrix of the composite specimens. The average initial yield stress, defined by backward extrapolation, was found at 58 MPa (8.42 ksi) from six specimens. Each test specimen was cycled from a minimum stress of 7.0 MPa (1.01 ksi) to maximum stress. The maximum stress was increased gradually, and at each cyclic load range a sufficient number of cycles was applied for the specimen to harden and shake down, i.e., resume elastic response. The test results are shown in Fig. 4. Maximum elastic or shakedown stress range was 149 MPa (21.6 ksi) and the fatigue endurance range was 140.6 MPa (20.4 ksi) at 2×10^6 cycles. Therefore, the magnitude of matrix yield stress Y to be used in shakedown limit calculations is equal to 70.3 MPa (10.2 ksi), i.e., to one-half of the endurance range. More representative results would be expected if the matrix specimens were tested in strain controlled mode at $R = -1$, which is more similar to the *in situ* cyclic stress regime of the aluminum matrix.

3. Unidirectional 6061-0 Al-B Test Results

Specimens were prepared from an eight-layer unidirectional plate and tested at three different values of the stress ratio, i.e., at $R = 0.1, 0.3, 0.5$. The results obtained for this group of specimens are summarized in Table II. In addition to the maximum stress S_{max} sustained for 2×10^6 cycles, the Table lists the value of $S_{sh} = 6.1Y/(1-R)$, which is the maximum stress calculated from the shakedown range shown in Table I. The last column shows maximum fiber stress σ_{max}^f at S_{max} , calculated with the assumption that $\sigma_{max}^m = Y = 70.3$ MPa (10.2 ksi) which is the lowest magnitude of matrix yield stress Y in the absence of extensive matrix damage.

The results indicate the difference in magnitude between the shakedown and endurance limits, in contrast with the results summarized in our 1975 paper [1]. Also, the present results seem to show an influence of the mean stress on the endurance limit, which was not in evidence in the earlier tests [1]. However, both the past and present results suggest that fiber stresses at endurance load levels are dependent on the load ratio R , and do not favor a fatigue criterion based solely on fiber strength. In fact, the σ_{max}^f estimates in Table II may be too conservative at higher S_{max} levels, because they do not reflect any damage effects which may be expected at high S_{max} .

A microscopic examination of several specimens tested for 2×10^6 cycles failed to reveal evidence of cracking in the matrix or of the fibers, in contrast to the results reported in [12]. However, we have obtained an indirect indication of internal damage in these specimens from measured changes in their elastic stiffness.

FIGURE 4

Fatigue test results for annealed aluminum matrix material.

TABLE II. Endurance and Shakedown Limits for Unidirectional 6061-0 Al-B ($v_f=0.45$)

R	S_{max} MPa	S_{sh} MPa	σ_{max}^f MPa (ksi)
0.1	800	476	1692 (245)
0.3	875	613	1858 (270)
0.5	950	858	2025 (294)

Fig. 5 shows the results together with the calculated shakedown range, $\Delta S_{sh} = (1-R)S_{sh} = 429$ MPa, from the third column of Table II. An empirical relationship between ΔS and percent drop in elastic modulus ΔE was found using a best fit regression analysis as $\Delta S = 481(1120.6)\exp(\Delta E)$ from the data points of Fig. 5 with correlation coefficient $R = 0.94$. Although the decrease in axial elastic stiffness is quite small in the unidirectional specimens, Fig. 5 shows that the shakedown range ΔS_{sh} is within the nine percent of the stress range ΔS_{dm} at which internal damage starts to appear.

The average tensile strength in static loading was found to be 1070 MPa. The actual results are shown in Fig. 6 together with the residual strength of fatigue-tested specimens which have exhibited a reduction of elastic stiffness after 2×10^6 cycles of loading.

4. 6061-0 Al-B Laminated Plate Specimens

Two laminate layouts were tested. One was a 15 layer $(0/\pm 45/90/0/\pm 45/\frac{1}{2}90)_S$, which will be referred to as Plate A; it has been investigated most extensively in

FIGURE 5

Change in elastic modulus of unidirectional specimens related to applied stress range ΔS .

FIGURE 6

Residual static strength of unidirectional specimens after 2×10^6 cycles of load

the course of this work. The other was an 8 layer $(0/\pm 45/90)_s$ plate, which will be referred to as Plate B. Table III summarizes the results of fatigue tests. In addition to the maximum stress S_{max} sustained for 2×10^6 cycles, the table shows $S_{sh} = (\Delta S_{sh}/Y) Y/(1-R)$, the maximum stress calculated from the shakedown range $(\Delta S_{sh}/Y)$ listed for each plate in Table I. Also shown is the S_{dm} , which is the highest stress level at which we have observed the onset of internal damage in test specimens as reflected in the changes of axial elastic modulus.

TABLE III. Endurance and Shakedown Limits
of Laminated Plates A and B

Layup	v_f	R	S_{max} MPa	S_{sh} MPa	S_{dm} MPa	Note
<u>Plate A</u>						
$(0/\pm 45/90/0/\pm 45/1/2 90)_s$	0.45	0.1	375*	212	218	15 layers
(UTS = 581 MPa)		0.3	375*	272	280	
<u>Plate B</u>						
$(0/\pm 45/90)_s$	0.33	0.1	226	203	189	8 layers
(UTS = 355 MPa)						

*Good (G) Specimens

Plate A specimens were tested at many stress levels. Elastic and secant moduli in the axial direction were monitored in each test. Results of these measurements can be regarded as an indication of the development of internal damage in the laminate during cyclic loading. These results are illustrated in Fig. 7, which indicates the change in the elastic modulus, and in Fig. 8 which indicates the change in the secant modulus at the relatively high level of 350 MPa. The change in elastic modulus is the one which suggests that damage has taken place; the change in secant modulus is affected by other phenomena, such as cyclic strain hardening of the matrix and is not a reliable indication of fatigue damage. Fig. 8 shows the characteristic distinction between specimens which did and did not fail at less than 2×10^6 cycles, i.e., an apparent arrest of damage growth in the surviving specimens, as opposed to continuing damage development in the failing ones.

Fig. 9 shows a family of curves indicating the change of elastic modulus with the number of cycles. Clearly, the higher the stress, the larger is the reduction in the magnitude of elastic modulus. However, each of the surviving specimens has apparently attained a relatively stable level of damage well before 1×10^6 cycles. Specimens tested at several different values of S_{max} showed rapid transitions to higher damage levels as the load increased.

Fig. 10 shows a relationship between stress range and elastic modulus change at 2×10^6 cycles for two levels of $R = 0.1$, and 0.3 . The results for $R = 0.1$ are the values shown at 2×10^6 in Fig. 9, scaled to represent stress range ΔS instead of S_{max} . It appears that the stress range, rather than mean stress, controls the extent of damage at 2×10^6 cycles but more data would be needed for a definite statement. The magnitude of the ΔS_{dm} range, for which damage was first observed, and ΔS_{sh} , the shakedown range, agree very well. An empirical relation between stress range ΔS and percent drop in elastic modulus ΔE was found using a statistical best

FIGURE 7

Change in elastic modulus of two Plate A specimens tested at high S_{max} .

FIGURE 8

Change in secant modulus of two Plate A specimens tested at high S_{max} .

FIGURE 9
Change in elastic modulus of Plate A specimens tested at different values of S_{max} .

FIGURE 10
Change in elastic modulus of Plate A specimens related to applied stress range ΔS .

fit regression analysis as $\Delta S = 196 (2.66)\exp(\Delta E)$ from the data points in Fig. 10 with correlation coefficient $\rho = 0.95$.

Fig. 11 shows results similar to those in Fig. 10, obtained for Plate B material. Again, there is good agreement between ΔS_{dm} and ΔS_{sh} . An empirical relation between ΔS and ΔE was found as $\Delta S = 166 (2.13)\exp(\Delta E)$ from the data points in Fig. 11 with correlation coefficient $\rho = 0.97$.

FIGURE 11

Change in elastic modulus of Plate B specimens related to applied stress range ΔS .

FIGURE 12

Residual static strength of Plate A specimens tested after 2×10^6 cycles of load.

The final stage of mechanical testing of some of the specimens cycled for 2×10^6 cycles has been a static test to failure. The residual strength values are shown in Fig. 12. Although the scatter is relatively large, there is a clear trend showing that specimens which had retained a large percentage of the original elastic stiffness during the 2×10^6 cycles of load have also retained much of their original static strength. The static strength data points are plotted in Fig. 12 at 100% of initial elastic modulus.

5. Microscopic Examination

Many fatigue-tested specimens were examined under an optical stereo microscope (40x) for evidence of damage. Most extensive examination was made on specimens from Plate A ($0/\pm 45/90/0/\pm 45/1/290$)_S; typical observations are illustrated in the following photographs. The internal damage was exposed by gradual etching of the aluminum matrix in a 30% HCl solution in distilled water. Fiber failure was detected only in specimens tested at stresses approaching the endurance limit. Substantial fatigue damage was detected well below this stress level in terms of stiffness changes. Examination of specimens which sustained such damage without failure revealed long cracks in the matrix which grow parallel to the fibers in the off-axis layers of the laminate. These cracks appear to be contained within the individual off-axis layers and do not extend beyond the nearest row of fibers which are not parallel to the matrix crack direction.

Fig. 13 shows the matrix cracks in the 45° layer of a Plate A specimen F-16, tested at $S_{\max} = 275$ MPa, $R = 0.3$ for 2×10^6 cycles. Notice that the cracks are partially hidden below the remaining 0° fibers, which are in the vertical direction in Fig. 13.

FIGURE 13

Cracks in the $+45^\circ$ layer in specimen F-16, Plate A. Tension axis and 0° fibers are in the horizontal direction.

Fig. 14 shows an example of higher crack density on a segment of the interface between $+45^\circ$ and -45° layers which has been exposed when the specimen failed and the interface delaminated. This particular specimen F-9 was tested at $S_{\max} = 425$ MPa, $R = 0.1$; it failed after 33,170 cycles.

FIGURE 14

Cracks meeting at the $\pm 45^\circ$ layer interface near fracture surface in specimen F-9, Plate A ($S_{\max} = 425$ MPa, $R = 0.1$, $N_f = 33,170$ cycles). Tension axis is in the horizontal direction.

Many photographs of this kind have been obtained. They clearly indicate the presence of crack systems in individual layers of the laminate, and occasional fiber failures. However, no fiber breaks were observed in the $\pm 45^\circ$ and 90° layers, except at fracture surfaces and in the immediate vicinity of some machined edges. In general, the damage caused by cutting the specimens with a diamond saw was very localized and could not be related to the long matrix cracks of the type shown in Fig. 13. Failure of 0° fibers was observed only in specimens tested above $S_{\max} = 325$ MPa, i.e., well above S_{sh} and S_{dm} found for Plate A, Table III. Fiber breaks detected at these high-er loads were limited to less than 10% of all fibers.

Long matrix cracks of the type shown in Fig. 13 and 14 were observed in specimens which exhibited a reduction of the elastic modulus during cyclic loading. These cracks grew to the edge of adjacent 0° and -45° fibers without causing fracture of these fibers. Attempts to find the origin of the $\pm 45^\circ$ cracks at cut side surfaces of the specimen were unsuccessful even after the sides were etched. Therefore, it is possible that these long cracks nucleated within the specimen, perhaps from initial flaws in the matrix. Crack interaction at lamina interfaces may also play a role, but localized crack systems in surface layers did not cause locally more intensive cracking in the next $\pm 45^\circ$ layer. The examination of matrix cracks under optical and scanning electron microscopes did not reveal significant delamination at fiber-matrix interfaces, or longitudinal splitting of the fibers. No fiber pullout or splitting was observed at fracture surfaces.

DISCUSSION OF RESULTS

Our results indicate that the applied stress amplitude at which significant stiffness reduction first starts to develop is approximately equal to the shakedown limit of the composite laminates tested in the present program. While the fatigue damage process is a complex one, and no simple model can be expected to give a complete understanding, the shakedown analysis appears to be a necessary part of any serious attempt to analyze the damage in metal matrix laminates. One hopes that more desirable answers to the problem will be found in terms of crack propagation mechanism through the laminate.

In any event, the shakedown analysis appears to provide an approximate, simple estimate of the stress amplitude at which damage starts to appear in the laminate. The analysis can be readily extended to multiaxial loading of the laminate, as well as to complex geometries. The shakedown limit can be found, in principle, for any program of variable cyclic loading, and for a large range of material properties.

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